
Data-driven decision support in custom manufacturing design¹

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Abstract: In the design for manufacturing, the choice of the best processing activities and production scheduling plays an important role. The aim of the research is to create an automated process estimation system based on the processing plan of previously manufactured artefacts, which supports the scheduling software in the case of a piece manufacturing environment. We present a method and corresponding similarity metrics and evaluate the performance of our method on a set of real-life manufacturing plans and design data.

Keywords: planning workflow, intelligent design, shape distance metrics, custom manufacturing

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1 Introduction

There are many possible ways to increase the efficiency and productivity of the production process. In addition to design for manufacturing and the choice of the best processing elements and parameters, production scheduling also plays an important role. The task of production scheduling is to distribute each individual production task among the available resources, i.e. to schedule the use of resources. In the case of component production, resources are machining tools (including the possibility for manual steps as well).

The basic information for scheduling is the operation sequence plan. The sequence of operations plan returns the skeleton of the manufacturing process, including the sequence of operations and the necessary execution time for these. The sequence of operations is fixed; an operation is a unit of technological design that can be carried out on a given piece of equipment without interrupting the process. In the case of machining technologies, the set of operations that can be carried out on a single machine in a single operation. The operation consists of operation elements.

Effective production schedules require the existence of a process plan, which is a challenge in the case of custom manufacturing, as not always a sequence of operations plan is produced with the depth, detail and accuracy of data to implement the schedule. The task of operation sequence planning is to compare machining needs and conceptual possibilities, to determine (select) the manufacturing methods, machine tools and equipment that can be used, and to determine the sequence of operations.

The similarity principle (analogy) can be implemented in many different ways in design. For more than 30 years, researchers have been developing automated tools for part classification, indexing and analysis, spanning a wide range of research areas (CAD/CAM, engineering design, knowledge representation, case-based inference, computer vision, pattern recognition, body modelling, shape modelling and computer graphics). The results of shape analysis show that it may be a suitable basis for the creation of new technologies for transforming geometry-centric engineering data into a knowledge base that can significantly improve the product realization process [15].

There are three basic reasons for looking for similarities. The first is cost estimation, which can (also) be done on the basis of similarity. The second is the desire to reuse parts in the design process, and the third is the development of sub-part families for more efficient process design [4].

The aim of the research is to create an automated process estimation system based on the process plan of known parts, which supports the scheduling software in the case of piece manufacturing environment.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. First, in Section 2 we look at the related works. Section 3 presents the overall concept that is used to process 3D models and estimate the workflows required to manufacture them. The inputs of the process and their evaluation are presented in Section 4. Similarity metrics and their

usage to compare 3D models are presented in Section 5. Section 6 presents the selection and the usage of the estimator models. We evaluate the presented approach in Section 7.

2 Related work

Similarity finding is a key issue of the analogy-based design principle.

Cardone et al. [3] investigate the similarity of rectangular parts produced by milling based on the similarity of the individual geometric elements. Thus, it decomposes the geometry and compares the individual elements. This analytical solution requires that the parts to be compared are built from predefined geometric elements, but this approach is less sensitive to the location of the elements. For each element, the algorithm assigns two vectors, an access vector, and an orientation vector.

Zhang and Zhou [18] use an integrated product information model (IPIM) to determine similarity for prismatic parts. First, they compare non-geometric data with rapidly reusable design documents or available resources. Then, geometric data and shape similarities are compared using a two-step evaluation algorithm in order to rank the similarity of reusable models. In the first step, the shapes of the models are classified by absolute angle and distance (AAD), and a vector support machine (SVM) excludes models that do not belong to the class of the model being searched. In the second step, a genetic algorithm (GA) is used to estimate the similarity of shape features based on shape, process, direction, and positional distribution. Geometric similarity is determined using the AAD algorithm. This involves randomly selecting points on the surface of the model using the Monte Carlo method and then determining the distance of each possible pair of points, which are represented by a histogram.

The key question of histogram-based similarity is what data is contained in the histogram that is being compared. Osada [13] investigated five different distance interpretations for histogram-based similarity: (1) A3 - angle enclosed by three randomly selected points; (2) D1 - distance between a fixed and a random surface point; (3) D2 - distance between two random surface points; (4) D3 - square root of the area of a triangle defined by three random surface points; (5) D4 - cube of the volume of a tetrahedron defined by four random surface points, presented later in Sec.5.1.

Cicek [6] searches for similar components by topological analysis of STEP models. The topology is defined using a matrix describing the neighbourhood of each geometric basis element. This is used to determine dimensional and non-dimensional similarity. Ma and Tian [12] investigate the similarity of CAD models both topologically by analyzing the CSG tree describing the relationship of each geometric primitive and by comparing the geometry using histograms generated

from the D2 distance definition. Chu and Hsu [5] search for similar parts by comparing the topology of the CAD model. In their study, they generated a shape-feature adjacency graph (FAG) and a topology graph (TG) based on the CAD model. The combined similarity of the graphs on the CAD models they studied proved to be more effective than comparing D2 distance histograms.

Harik and Barakat [9] investigate the similarity of the geometric elements that make up parts and their relationships. They first determine the relationship of each geometric element based on a STEP format model of the part and generate a relationship graph. Then, by analyzing the graph, it creates a machining graph to search for similar parts. The similarity is therefore the similarity in manufacturing. The implementation was done for slab-based parts, where the types and number of building blocks were limited. Kusiak and Cho [10] investigate the design of component groups using process data. They create a machine-part occurrence matrix and group parts that occur on the same machines into a group. A method for the structural representation of models is presented by Renner and Stroud [16]. The method is called Medial Axis Transformation (MAT). They replace pairs of related elements with vertices and connect them. The vertex can be a bisector point or a corner point. In the case of MAT, the bisector point of the segment connecting the two elements. In the global structure of a positive object, only the faces are represented by nodes, whereas in the global structure of a negative object (negative MAT), all edges and vertices are also represented as nodes.

3 Overview of the approach

In this section, we introduce our innovative approach to processing the available information and train our models for accurate prediction. Later, the trained models are used to predict the necessary production steps for the new products.

Figure 1: Model processing and workflow estimation process

3.1 Model processing and workflow estimation process

In this section, we present our model processing and workflow estimation process, depicted on Figure 1: Model processing and workflow estimation process Figure 1.

There are two main tasks that our process solves:

- 1) processing models for the training of the predictive models, and
- 2) processing of the next product and predicting the production steps.

The inputs of the process:

- **Product data:** the product data consists of the 3D models of the workpieces, the manufacturing workflows assigned to these models, and the product metadata. The product metadata contains valuable information regarding the ordered and manufactured workpieces, e.g. the material of the products and required surface treatment methods, which have to be considered during the planning of the manufacturing workflow.

Training In the case of building and training estimator models we use historical product data, provided by Component Ltd. These historical data consist of a) industrial CAD models, b) the respective manufacturing workflows of the workpieces represented by the CAD models, and c) the product metadata of the workpiece.

Estimation In case of new orders, CAD models and product metadata (e.g. the material of the products and required surface treatment methods) are provided by the customers, these models must be processed and extended with derived metrics to serve as a basis for prediction of the manufacturing workflow of the order.

- **Potential manufacturing steps:** the list of steps that can be performed to manufacture the workpieces, see Section 4.1 for details. Note that in our case, these steps were applied at the premises of Component Ltd, however, the method is agnostic to the concrete company.

Model processing phase:

- **Automated processing of CAD files:** calculating the similarity metrics and the derived measures presented in Section 5. The similarity metrics will be used to find the best match across the historical models, while the derived measures will support the estimation of workflow steps.
- **Comparing models:** comparison of the models resulting in their pairwise similarity metrics. In the case of processing historical data, the model similarity is used to build the estimator model. In the case of new orders, the model similarity is used to predict the steps required to manufacture the workpiece.

Training phase:

- **Estimator model training:** training of the workflow estimator models using the calculated similarity and the manufacturing workflows of the
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historical CAD models, and the applicable manufacturing steps, using the decision support algorithms presented in Section 6.1.

Estimation phase:

- **Estimating manufacturing steps:** predicting the steps required to manufacture a new order using the method presented later in Section 6.2.

4 Evaluation of historical data

Before we can train the estimator models, we had to process the historical data. During the project, we analyzed about 3300 historical manufacturing workflows and their respective 3D models, produced by Component Ltd. in recent years. In this section, we first analyze the potential manufacturing steps of Component Ltd., then we briefly evaluate the manufacturing workflows compiled from the potential manufacturing steps.

4.1 Potential manufacturing steps

The Component Ltd. keeps records of eighteen different manufacturing steps, including industry standard steps, e.g. turning, milling, sawing, etc., surface treatment methods, and the following other steps: manual work, outsourced work, and digital measuring.

We divided the eighteen manufacturing steps into two categories according to their role in the manufacturing plan estimation process:

- **Optional steps:** Optional steps can be included in the manufacturing process. Our task is to estimate whether these steps are needed for a given workpiece, and if they are needed, we compute the time required to execute them. Such steps are turning, milling, sawing, etc. The time required for these steps depends on the dimensions and material of the workpiece.
 - **Obligatory steps:** These steps are ordered by the customer and included in the product metadata, e.g. surface treatment methods, or need expert review, e.g. CAD-CAM design, digital measuring. These steps are omitted from the estimation process as their application depends on external factors.
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Table 1: List of the possible manufacturing steps

Manufacturing step	Code	
CAD-CAM design	A	Not estimated
Cutting	B	Not estimated
Turning	C	Estimated
CNC machining	CNC	Not estimated
2D milling	D1	Estimated
5D milling	D5	Estimated
Hard milling	E	Estimated
Grinding	F	Not estimated
Drilling	FM	Not estimated
Wire EDM	G	Estimated
Heat treatment	H1	Not estimated
Eloxation / Anodization	H2	Not estimated
Manual work	X_hand	Estimated
Radial drill	I	Not estimated
Work done by a subcontractor	X_sub	Estimated
Other	X	Not estimated
3D measurement	3D	Not estimated
Validation	ZV	Not estimated

4.2 Historical manufacturing workflows

We analyzed about 3300 historical manufacturing workflows compiled from 10000 manufacturing steps analyzed in Section 4.1. These manufacturing workflows were designed by experts. Our goal is to support the decision-making process of the experts who design the manufacturing workflows, thus we analyzed only the planned manufacturing workflows and not the actual manufacturing workflows executed in the factories.

The histogram of the lengths of the manufacturing workflows can be seen on Figure 2. In most cases, the manufacturing workflows contain three different manufacturing steps, with 2D milling (D1) being the most frequently used manufacturing step.

Figure 2: Histogram of the length of the analyzed workflows

5 Similarity between models

Finding similarity between models has a number of applications, one of which is estimating the manufacturing workflow. The estimated workflow then can be used to estimate the cost of the production or optimizing the production line.

The main similarity assessment algorithms for component and technology design can be classified into the following seven categories [4][8][18][11]: (1) non-geometry property based similarity, (2) geometry property based similarity, (3) histogram-based similarity, (4) image comparison of details, (5) similarity based on a function of space, (6) graph-based similarity, (7) similarity based on features.

The density function-based metrics measure the distances between various points of the surface of the model, which can be used to describe the dimensions of the model. In the case of two similar models, small differences, e.g. a different number of holes or different positions of holes can lead to significant differences in the density functions of models, while their production workflow could be the very similar. In the case of topology-based similarity metrics, the dimensions of the models are ignored, this means that models with the same number of holes, but in different positions are very similar to each other, however, models with significant size differences are also very similar to each other, even though their production workflow can differ, e.g. because of the limitations of the machines.

In order to give an accurate estimation for the manufacturing workflow of a new order, we have to cover different aspects of the 3D models to find the most similar

historical model to the new order. Thus, we apply both density function-based and topology-based metrics.

In this section, we first present the selected density function-based similarity metrics and their usage in the model comparison. Next, as a new contribution, we present topology-based similarity metrics and their usage in the model comparison. Finally, we describe the derived measures, which are later used in the estimator training and the workflow estimation steps.

5.1 Application of selected density function-based metrics

According to the literature, we have chosen density function-based metrics to compare the similarity of two object given in a 3D model.

Osada [13] investigated five different distance interpretations for histogram-based similarity:

- A3: Measures the angle between three random points on the surface of a 3D model.
- D1: Measures the distance between a fixed point and one random point on the surface. We use the centroid of the boundary of the model as the fixed point.
- D2: Measures the distance between two random points on the surface.
- D3: Measures the square root of the area of the triangle between three random points on the surface.
- D4: Measures the cube root of the volume of the tetrahedron between four random points on the surface.

Figure 3: Density function-based metrics

To calculate the metric value for a given model, we sample the surface of the model and calculate the distances between the sampled points based on the metric. This sampling corresponds to the sampling of the Probability Distribution Function (PDF) of the metric, interpreted by its histogram.

Figure 4 shows the histogram of the D2 metric for one particular plan (called *shape*). In this case, it shows the observed PDF of D2 distance values calculated in this case on 20.000 point pairs.

Figure 4: Histogram of D2 metric of a Shape

The Kolmogorov–Smirnov test [1] (KS test) is a nonparametric statistical test to decide whether two samples came from the same distribution. To determine the similarity of two 3D models, we perform a two-sample on the samples of the two models. The P-value of the KS test tells us how likely is that the samples came from the same distribution, which we can interpret as how likely is that samples came from the same model.

5.2 Definition and application of topology-based metrics

We defined similarity metrics based on the adjacent faces of the surface of the 3D models. The similarity metrics are derived from 11 types of surfaces: planes, cylinders, cones, spheres, toruses, Bézier surfaces, B-spline surfaces, surfaces of revolutions, surfaces of extrusions, offset surfaces, and other custom types of surfaces.

For a given surface S_i in model M_i , we collect the types of those surfaces that have at least one common edge with S_i . These collections are called *adjacent surface sets*, and an *adjacent surface set* is a function mapping the types of the adjacent surfaces into the number of occurrences, represented as a multiset. A multiset m over a set S is a function $m: S \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}^{\oplus+}$, where $m(S)$ is the number of occurrences of the element $s \in S$ in m .

Formally a multiset $a_i = \{[t_{S_i}, m(t_{S_i})]; [t_{S_j}, m(t_{S_j})]; \dots; [t_{S_k}, m(t_{S_k})]\}$ is an *adjacent surface set*, where S_j and S_k are adjacent surfaces to S_i ; t_{S_i} , t_{S_j} , t_{S_k} are the types of the respective surfaces; $t_{S_i} \neq t_{S_j} \neq t_{S_k}$; $m(t_{S_i})$, $m(t_{S_j})$, $m(t_{S_k})$ are the number of adjacent surfaces of types t_{S_i} , t_{S_j} , t_{S_k} respectively.

The topology of model M_i is a function mapping all the *adjacent surface sets* observed in M_i into the number of occurrences, represented as a multiset. Formally, multiset $A_i = \{[a_1, m(a_1)]; [a_2, m(a_2)]; \dots; [a_n, m(a_n)]\}$ is the topology of model

M_i , where a_i is an *adjacent surface set* observed in M_i and $m(a_i)$ is the number of times a_i was observed in M_i .

To calculate the similarity of the models, we transform the multisets describing the models to vectors, and calculate the *cosine distance* of these vectors. To transform the *topology* multisets into vectors, we have to define an ordering of the elements of the multisets. To achieve this, we order the universe of the *topology* multisets in the order of the first observation of its elements. The vector transformed from a multiset M_i is defined as follows:

$$v_{M_i}[j] = \begin{cases} m_{M_i}(a_j), & \text{if } a_j \in M_i \\ 0, & \text{if } a_j \notin M_i \end{cases}, \forall a_j \in \Omega$$

We defined five topology-based similarity metrics. They only differ in how the adjacent surface sets are defined, and how the number of occurrences of the adjacent surface sets are registered in the models. The relationships between the topology-based similarity metrics are shown on Figure 5. Metric1 is the most concrete metric, Metric2 and Metric3 abstract different aspects of Metric1, while Metric4 abstracts both aspects of Metric1.

Figure 5: Relations between the topology-based metrics

Consider the example model a) shown in Figure 6. We see a cube with four holes going through from top to bottom. This is modelled with six plane surfaces (S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4, S_5 and S_6 respectively) and four cylinder surfaces (S_7, S_8, S_9 and S_{10} respectively) connecting S_1 and S_6 .

Figure 6: Examples of the adjacent surfaces

Metric1 The first similarity metric registers the types of all the adjacent surfaces to define the adjacent surface sets and counts all the occurrences of a given adjacent surface set to determine the multiset describing the model.

In example model a) in Figure 6, S_1 is a plane, it has four adjacent plane surfaces (S_2, S_3, S_4, S_5) and four adjacent cylinder surfaces (S_7, S_8, S_9, S_{10}). S_2 is a plane and has four adjacent plane surfaces (S_1, S_3, S_4, S_6). S_7 is a cylinder and has two adjacent plane surfaces (S_1, S_6). S_6 has the same adjacent surface types as S_1 . S_3, S_4 and S_5 have the same adjacent surface types as S_2 . S_8, S_9 and S_{10} have the same surface types as S_7 . Thus, the registered adjacent surface sets are the following:

- $a_{S_1} = a_{S_6} = \{[plane, 5]; [cylinder, 4]\}$
- $a_{S_2} = a_{S_3} = a_{S_4} = a_{S_5} = \{[plane, 5]\}$
- $a_{S_7} = a_{S_8} = a_{S_9} = a_{S_{10}} = \{[cylinder, 1]; [plane, 2]\}$

The multiset describing the topology of the example model is $A_a = \{[a_{S_1}, 2]; [a_{S_2}, 4]; [a_{S_7}, 4]\}$. Note that the adjacent surface sets are in the order of their first observation. This property is used during the calculation of the similarity of different models.

Metric2 The second similarity metric registers the types of all the adjacent surfaces to define the adjacent surface sets. As an abstraction of *Metric1*, it only registers whether a given adjacent surface set is observed in the given model. Thus, the registered adjacent surface sets are the same as in the case of *Metric1*, but the multiset representing the example model a) is $A_a = \{[a_{S_1}, 1]; [a_{S_2}, 1]; [a_{S_7}, 1]\}$. In the case of example model b), a model with a fifth hole going through S_1 and S_6 would be considered the same as the example model a), however, it slightly differs in the case of *Metric1*. Furthermore, in the case of example model c), where the fifth hole goes through S_2 and S_4 , they cannot be distinguished by using *Metric2*, even though there might be differences in the sequence of the operations.

Metric3 The third similarity metric registers only the set of the adjacent surfaces to define the adjacent surface sets and counts all the occurrences of a given adjacent surface set to compile the vector describing the model. The third similarity metric

is again an abstraction of Metric1, but in this case, the registered adjacent surface sets are abstracted. The registered adjacent surface sets are the following:

- $a_{S1} = a_{S6} = \{[plane, 2]; [cylinder, 1]\}$
- $a_{S2} = a_{S3} = a_{S4} = a_{S5} = \{[plane, 2]\}$
- $a_{S7} = a_{S8} = a_{S9} = a_{S10} = \{[cylinder, 1]; [plane, 1]\}$

The multiset representing example model a) is $A_a = \{[a_{S1}, 2]; [a_{S2}, 4]; [a_{S7}, 4]\}$.

Metric4 As an abstraction of both Metric2 and Metric3 the fourth similarity metric registers only the set of the adjacent surfaces to define the adjacent surface sets and only registers whether a given adjacent surface set can be observed in the given model. Thus, the registered adjacent surface sets are the same as in the case of Metric3, but the multiset representing the example model a) is $A_a = \{[a_{S1}, 1]; [a_{S2}, 1]; [a_{S7}, 1]\}$

Metric5 Collecting all the possible adjacent surface sets for the universe of the multisets can be computationally heavy in the case of large, diverse model sets. Runtime registration of an observed adjacent surface set can require iterating through a large multiset, where the inclusion can only be decided after iterating through the whole multiset since the adjacent surface sets are registered in the order of observation. We defined the fifth metric to solve the computational problem with a predefined, fixed-length universe of the multisets. In the case of the fifth metric, before the processing of the models we define the universe of the multisets as the possible pairs of the surface types: $\Omega = \{\{plane, plane\}; \{plane, cylinder\}; \{plane, cone\}; \dots; \{extrusion, other\}; \{offset, offset\}; \{offset, other\}; \{other, other\}\}$. The multiset representing the given model is the complete multiset over the universe. The multiset representing example model a) is described as follows

$$A_a = \{\{\{plane, plane\}, 24\}; \{\{plane, cylinder\}, 4\}; \{\{plane, cone\}, 0\}; \dots; \{\{other, other\}, 0\}\}.$$

5.3 Augmentation with derived measures

We describe additional features of the models which are later used by the workflow estimator models.

We define the bounding box of the 3D models to approximate the volume of the initial workpieces from which the final workpieces are machined. The ratio between the volume of the final workpiece and the volume of the bounding box gives a sense of how much material must be removed from the initial workpiece to manufacture the final workpiece. The ratio between the surface area of the final workpiece and the surface area of the bounding box gives a sense of the complexity of machining the final workpiece because the larger change in the surface area leads to more complex manufacturing steps; thus we can argue about the complexity of the steps that are required to manufacture the final workpiece.

The necessity of some manufacturing steps is decidable directly from the 3D model. If the initial workpiece is cylindrical, we can be almost certain that turning is needed to manufacture the workpiece. We also search for holes in the model, which tells us if drilling is needed to manufacture the workpiece. Finally, if the model contains surfaces defined by splines there must be expert supervision in the manufacturing workflow.

6 Estimation process and analysis

In this section, we present the machine learning algorithms used for decision support. After that, we present the application of the decision support algorithms to estimate the manufacturing workflows of the workpieces.

6.1 Machine learning algorithms for decision support

6.1.1 Decision Trees

The Decision Tree learning algorithm [14] is a supervised learning approach. The leaves of the Decision Tree are the possible outcomes of the target variable and the inner nodes are the decisions based on the input features. Decision trees with discrete target variables are called classification trees (Decision Tree Classifiers), whereas decision trees where the target variable can take continuous values are called regression trees (Decision Tree Regressors).

Decision trees can handle both numerical and categorical data. Unlike most machine learning algorithms, the decision trees are white-box models, thus the importance of each input feature is known. The decisions made by the decision tree can be supported by the structure of the decision tree, which represents the training data.

During our work to estimate the time of the steps of the manufacturing workflow, we applied Decision Tree Regressors.

6.1.2 Random Forests

The random forest is an ensemble learning method [2], where several smaller decision trees are used together. During the training phase, both the training data and the training variables are split randomly, so there is a low probability that any of the resulting trees were trained under the same condition. This made the Random Forests method more robust than a simple Decision Tree and made it more immune to overfitting, which is a general problem of machine learning algorithms.

During our work to predict the steps of the manufacturing workflow, we applied Random Forests due to their robustness to faults and overfitting; in addition to the advantages of the Decision Trees.

6.2 Workflow estimation process

Estimating complete manufacturing workflows is a challenging task. Instead of estimating the complete workflow, we are focusing on estimating individual steps one by one. The workflow estimation process contains three steps and can be seen in Figure 7:

- **Predict first step:** prediction of the first manufacturing step,
- **Predict next step:** prediction of the next manufacturing step using Random Forests
- **Calculate time for steps:** calculating the time of the whole manufacturing process, from the time required by the individual steps, using Decision Tree Regressors, including the additional steps added by the customer.

Figure 7: Estimation process of the manufacturing workflow

6.2.1 Prediction of the next manufacturing step

To estimate the next manufacturing step, we trained a Random Forest for each manufacturing step that must be estimated (see Table 1) and an additional one that represents the end of the workflow. The inputs of each Random Forest are the same, namely: the current step, the position of the step to be estimated, the derived measures presented in Section 5.3, the material of the workpiece, the manufacturing steps that are not estimated, and the type of the previous steps. The output of each Random Forest is whether the given manufacturing step should be included as the next step and its confidence. This prediction process of the next manufacturing steps continues until the output of the Random Forest representing the end of the workflow has the highest confidence.

Figure 8 shows the importance of the input variables as observed during the training of the Random Forest method which selects the next step of the production workflow. The importance of the variables shows that the most important variable of the Random Forests is the current manufacturing step. This means that each step is highly dependent on the previous step, thus the estimation of the first step is critical since an incorrectly chosen first step can lead to incorrect manufacturing

workflows. We evaluated several methods to predict the first step of the workflow, including additional Random Forests trained specifically to predict the first step, and similarity-based methods based on the metrics presented in Section 5.

Figure 8: Importance of the input features of the Random Forests

6.2.2 Estimating the time of the manufacturing workflow

After predicting the manufacturing workflow, we extend the workflow with the manufacturing steps ordered by the customer, e.g. surface treatment methods. Finally, our algorithms calculate the time required to complete each step on the workpiece.

To estimate the time of the manufacturing workflow, we trained Decision Tree Regressors for cutting (B), turning (C), 2D milling (D1), 5D milling (D5), hard milling (E), grinding (F), and wire EDM (G) manufacturing steps. We assigned fixed manufacturing times for the rest of the possible manufacturing steps based on the experts' decisions. The inputs of each Decision Tree Regressor are the same, namely: the derived measures presented in Section 5.3 and the material of the workpiece.

7 Results

We evaluate the presented decision support method on 1000 randomly selected historical models and their manufacturing workflows. We measured 1) the number of cases when the estimated first step matches the real first step, 2) the number of cases when the estimated workflow (excluding the not predictable steps and the manufacturing times) matches the real workflows, and 3) how much the predicted workflow matches the real workflow calculated with the normalized Hamming distance as follows:

- σ is a manufacturing step from the set of possible manufacturing steps,
- σ^* is the sequence of manufacturing steps,
- $w \in \sigma^*$ is a manufacturing workflow,
- $w^i \in \sigma$ is the i^{th} manufacturing step of workflow w ,
- $|w|$ is the length of workflow w ,
- $match: \sigma \times \sigma \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ is a function, where
$$match(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \sigma_1 = \sigma_2 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$
- $H = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{\min(|p|,|r|)} match(p^i, r^i)}{\max(|p|,|r|)}$ is the normalized Hamming distance, where $p, r \in \sigma^*$ are the predicted and the real manufacturing workflows respectively.

The most critical step in the workflow estimation process is the selection of the first step of the workflow. We compared 13 different methods to estimate the first step of the workflows, summarized in Table 2.

First, we initiated the workflow estimation process with the first step of the manufacturing workflow defined by the experts. This resulted in 87% fully matching workflows and 89% average normalized Hamming distance. Because the rest of the workflow estimation process is the same for each compared method, this is the limitation of our current decision support method.

Next, we used random forests trained for the estimation of the first manufacturing step. This method resulted in 92% matching first steps, 79% fully matching workflows and 87% average normalized Hamming distance.

Based on the similarity metrics presented in Section 5 we selected the most similar model to each test model and chose their first manufacturing steps to the workflow estimation process. In the case of the density function-based similarity metrics, the best-performing metric was the D1 metric in which case the first steps matched in 77% of the test models, there were 67% fully matching workflows and 78% average workflow matching. In the case of the topology-based similarity metrics both Metric1, Metric4, and Metric5 performed similarly, resulting in 85% matching first

steps, ~75% fully matching workflows, and ~83% average normalized Hamming distance.

After analyzing these results, we found that when the Random Forests method predicts turning (C), 2D milling (D1), or wire EDM (G) as the first step, it is correct in 90% of the cases. We also found that when the first step is hard milling (E), manual work (X_hand), or work done by a subcontractor (X_sub), Topology Metric1 is the most precise. The combination of the Random Forests and the Topology Metric1 methods resulted in 93% matching first steps, 81% fully matching workflows, and 88% average normalized Hamming distance, which is more accurate than using them separately (“Combination of selection methods”).

The results of the evaluation are summarized in Table 2 and the true positive rate of the predicted steps by each method is shown in Figure 9-Figure 14 and the number of manufacturing steps selected as first steps by each method is shown in Figure 15.

With the presented results, we showed that our model processing and workflow estimation process can be used to support the decision-making process of the experts working in custom manufacturing design. We showed that in 81% of the cases, we can fully estimate the required manufacturing workflow. We must emphasize that the presented process is a decision-support process, which always requires expert review. The presented approach is generic and can be used in other companies as well, but it must always be tailored to the individual company because of the differences in the possible manufacturing steps and in the manufacturing workflows in general.

Figure 9: True positive rate of estimating manufacturing steps using the real first step

Figure 10: True positive rate of estimating the manufacturing steps using Random Forests based first step

Table 2: Results of the evaluation

First step selection method		First step matching	Total workflow matching	Average workflow matching
Real first step		100%	87%	89%
Estimation based	Random forests	92%	79%	87%
Density function-based similarity metrics	A3	69%	60%	73%
	D1	77%	67%	78%
	D2	70%	61%	74%
	D3	69%	60%	73%
	D4	68%	59%	73%
Topology-based similarity metrics	Metric1	85%	74%	82%
	Metric2	78%	70%	80%
	Metric3	68%	59%	73%
	Metric4	85%	75%	83%
	Metric5	85%	76%	84%
Combination of selection methods		93%	81%	88%

Figure 11: True positive rate of estimating the manufacturing steps using Topology Metric1 based first step

Figure 12: True positive rate of estimating the manufacturing steps using Topology Metric5 based first step

Figure 13: True positive rate of estimating the manufacturing steps using Density metric D1 based first step

Figure 14: True positive rate of estimating the manufacturing steps using the Combination-based first step

Figure 15: Number of manufacturing steps selected as first step by each metric

8 Conclusion and future research

In this paper we presented a method to support the intelligent planning of manufacturing workflows, based on the knowledge on previous operations of a company. The suggested method takes 3D models of shapes and product requirements as input, and -using models trained on the previous 3D models and manufacturing processes of the company- estimates what steps, in which order and with what preliminary cost have to be estimated to create the product defined by the model and the user requirements.

Our method is based on a set of similarity/distance metrics defined to estimate the similarity of shapes in terms of their geometric and topological properties. We used a combination of evaluation based on these metrics and machine learning methods considering derived characteristics of these shapes to estimate the manufacturing workflow needed to create a shape.

We evaluated our method on the dataset of Component Ltd, and found that a combination of the selected metrics can effectively support this learning method. Our approach showed promising result in determining the steps which can help the creation of early manufacturing design plans and, enriched by operational information such as resource parameters and cost, a basis for a quote.

There are quite a number of future research steps which could improve the method and we can also benefit from the lessons learned here in other domains.

First, intelligent methods could be applied to develop different metrics combinations to find the best metric suite for a given question, i.e., create composite metrics to find the best similar shape from the past for a given type of manufacturing steps. We are also considering to introduce multi-aspect categorization for shapes and apply the distance metrics to find the best match within a category/group of shapes.

For a more generic application of the suggested multi-set metrics, we are investigating the applicability of these in other domains, e.g., in the testing of self-driving vehicles.

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